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Numerical Solution of the One-Dimensional Poisson Problem via Iterative Methods and Sparse Matrices

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Abstract

We present the numerical solution of the one-dimensional Poisson problem using sparse matrix structures and iterative methods. We analyze the performance of the Gauss-Seidel and Successive Over-Relaxation (SOR) methods applied to the resulting linear systems obtained via finite difference discretization. Numerical experiments illustrate the convergence behavior and efficiency of these methods.

keywords: Poisson problem, iterative methods, sparse matrices

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Introduction

Diagonally Dominant and Invertible Matrices

1. **Definition 1.** A matrix V of order n is diagonally dominant if

$$|v_{ii}| \geq \sum_{j=1}^n |v_{ij}|,$$

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and it is strictly diagonally dominant if

$$|v_{ii}| > \sum_{j=1}^n |v_{ij}|,$$

for all $j \neq i$ and $i = 1, \dots, n$.

2. **Lemma.** If a matrix V is strictly diagonally dominant, then V is invertible.
3. **Proof.** The proof of this lemma can be found in reference [2] p.19.

Sparse Matrices

4. The number of nonzero elements of a sparse matrix V is the count of entries in its sparsity pattern, denoted by $nnz(V)$, abbreviation of *number of non-zeros*. The following definition does not provide a precise characterization of sparse matrices, but rather an approach based on an essential property.
5. **Definition 2.** Given a matrix $V_{n \times m} \in \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m$, with entries v_{ij} , the number of nonzero elements satisfies $nnz(V) \leq nm$. The density of V is given by

$$s = \frac{nnz(V)}{nm} \leq \frac{1}{2}.$$

6. When $s < \frac{1}{2}$, most entries of the matrix are zero, which characterizes *sparse matrices*. Thus, the zero matrix and the identity matrix are examples of sparse matrices.
7. **Statement.** Let S be the set of matrices of order $n \times m$ and V the set of sparse matrices of order $n \times m$. Then V is not a vector subspace of S , since it does not satisfy closure under vector addition.

Computational Implementation of Sparse Matrices

8. Sparse matrices mainly contain zero entries, allowing more efficient storage by recording only nonzero elements and their positions. This requires specific techniques to optimize memory usage.

9. Many programming languages use indexing starting at 0, which facilitates element access and aligns better with memory management.
10. Thus, the following three techniques are the most popular for implementing sparse matrices.
11. **Coordinate Format (COO)**: In this format, each nonzero element is stored together with its coordinates (row and column) in three arrays:
 1. `valueArray`: nonzero values;
 2. `rowIndexArray`: row indices of the nonzero values;
 3. `columnIndexArray`: column indices of the nonzero values.
12. **Compressed Row Storage (CRS)**: The nonzero elements are stored efficiently as follows:
 1. `valueArray`: values of the nonzero elements, stored sequentially, row by row;
 2. `columnIndexArray`: indices of the columns corresponding to the values in `valueArray`;
 3. `rowPointerArray`: indices that indicate where each row begins in `valueArray`, with an additional element at the end to indicate the termination of the last row.
13. **Compressed Column Storage (CCS)**: This format is efficient for operations involving column access, such as matrix-vector multiplication. Its structure is similar to CRS, but the elements are stored column by column:
 1. `valueArray`: values of the nonzero elements, stored by column;
 2. `rowIndexArray`: indices of the corresponding rows;
 3. `columnPointerArray`: indices that indicate where each column begins in `valueArray`, with an additional element at the end to indicate the termination of the last column.
14. These formats help optimize both storage and operations involving sparse matrices.

Linear Iterative Methods

Gauss–Seidel Method

15. Considering the linear system $Vx = h$, of order n , with $\det V \neq 0$, we have

$$\begin{cases} v_{11}x_1 + v_{12}x_2 + \cdots + v_{1n}x_n = h_1 \\ v_{21}x_1 + v_{22}x_2 + \cdots + v_{2n}x_n = h_2 \\ v_{31}x_1 + v_{32}x_2 + \cdots + v_{3n}x_n = h_3 \\ \vdots \\ v_{n1}x_1 + v_{n2}x_2 + \cdots + v_{nn}x_n = h_n. \end{cases}$$

16. By decomposing the matrix V into a lower triangular matrix L , a diagonal matrix D , and an upper triangular matrix R , we obtain

$$V = L + D + R,$$

where:

$L = (l_{ij})$ corresponds to the lower triangular matrix;

$D = (d_{ij})$ corresponds to the diagonal matrix;

$R = (r_{ij})$ corresponds to the upper triangular matrix.

17. Let us assume that $\det D \neq 0$, so that the matrix D is invertible. The entries of these matrices are given by

$$l_{ij} = \begin{cases} v_{ij}, & i > j, \\ 0, & i \leq j, \end{cases} \quad d_{ij} = \begin{cases} v_{ij}, & i = j, \\ 0, & i \neq j, \end{cases} \quad r_{ij} = \begin{cases} v_{ij}, & i < j, \\ 0, & i \geq j. \end{cases}$$

18. Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (L + D + R)x &= h, \\ Dx &= -(R + L)x + h, \\ Dx &= -Rx - Lx + h, \\ x &= -(D^{-1})Rx - (D^{-1})Lx + (D^{-1})h. \end{aligned}$$

19. Consequently, the iterative process is given by

$$x^{(k+1)} = -(D^{-1})Rx^{(k)} - (D^{-1})Lx^{(k)} + (D^{-1})h,$$

or, equivalently,

$$x^{(k+1)} = -D^{-1}(R + L)x^{(k)} + D^{-1}h.$$

20. Let us now consider the linear system $V^*x = h^*$, where $V^* = L^* + I + R^*$, $h^* = \begin{pmatrix} h_i \\ v_{ii} \end{pmatrix}$, with $v_{ii} \neq 0$, and

$$l_{ij}^* = \begin{cases} \frac{v_{ij}}{v_{ii}}, & i > j, \\ 0, & i \leq j, \end{cases} \quad d_{ij}^* = \begin{cases} \frac{v_{ij}}{v_{ii}}, & i = j, \\ 0, & i \neq j, \end{cases} \quad r_{ij}^* = \begin{cases} \frac{v_{ij}}{v_{ii}}, & i < j, \\ 0, & i \geq j. \end{cases}$$

21. Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V^*x = h^* &\Rightarrow (L^*x + Ix + R^*x) = h^*, \\ L^*x + Ix &= -(R^*x) + h^*, \\ x &= -(L^* + I)^{-1}R^*x + (L^* + I)^{-1}h^*. \end{aligned}$$

22. That is

$$\begin{cases} x_1^{(k+1)} = -v_{12}^*x_2^{(k)} - v_{13}^*x_3^{(k)} - \dots - v_{1n}^*x_n^{(k)} + h_1^* \\ x_2^{(k+1)} = -v_{21}^*x_1^{(k+1)} - v_{23}^*x_3^{(k)} - \dots - v_{2n}^*x_n^{(k)} + h_2^* \\ x_3^{(k+1)} = -v_{31}^*x_1^{(k+1)} - v_{32}^*x_2^{(k+1)} - \dots - v_{3n}^*x_n^{(k)} + h_3^* \\ \vdots \\ x_n^{(k+1)} = -v_{n1}^*x_1^{(k+1)} - v_{n2}^*x_2^{(k+1)} - \dots - v_{n,n-1}^*x_{n-1}^{(k+1)} + h_n^*. \end{cases}$$

23. This system can be represented by the following equation:

$$x_i^{(k)} = \frac{1}{v_{ii}} \left[h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij}x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij}x_j^{(k-1)} \right],$$

since the Gauss–Seidel method updates each variable at each iteration using the most recently available values of the other variables, which generally results in faster convergence. Thus, the method takes advantage of newly computed information to improve the accuracy of the approximations.

SOR Method

24. The Successive Over-Relaxation (SOR) method is an iterative technique derived from the Gauss–Seidel method, with the objective of accelerating the convergence of linear systems, especially those whose convergence is slow.
25. **Definition 3.** Let $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ be an approximation to the solution of the linear system $Vx = h$. The residual vector $r = h - Vx$ is associated with each computation of a component of the approximation of the solution vector in procedures such as the Gauss–Seidel method.
26. The objective of this method is to generate a sequence of approximations that causes the residual vectors to converge rapidly to zero. For the Gauss–Seidel method, we denote the residual vector by

$$r_i^{(k)} = (r_{1i}^{(k)}, r_{2i}^{(k)}, \dots, r_{ni}^{(k)})^T,$$

associated with the approximation

$$x_i^{(k)} = (x_1^{(k)}, x_2^{(k)}, \dots, x_{i-1}^{(k)}, x_i^{(k-1)}, \dots, x_n^{(k-1)})^T.$$

27. The m -th component of $r_i^{(k)}$ is given by

$$r_{mi}^{(k)} = h_m - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{mj} x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i}^n v_{mj} x_j^{(k-1)}.$$

28. Similarly, the i -th component of $r_i^{(k)}$ is given by

$$r_{ii}^{(k)} = h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij} x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)} - v_{ii} x_i^{(k-1)}.$$

29. Thus,

$$v_{ii} x_i^{(k-1)} + r_{ii}^{(k)} = h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij} x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)}.$$

30. In the Gauss–Seidel method, we have seen that the i -th component of $x^{(k)}$ is given by (23), that is,

$$x_i^{(k)} = \frac{1}{v_{ii}} \left[h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij} x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)} \right].$$

31. Since

$$v_{ii}x_i^{(k)} = h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij}x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij}x_j^{(k-1)},$$

it follows that

$$r_{ii}^{(k)} + v_{ii}x_i^{(k-1)} = v_{ii}x_i^{(k)}.$$

32. Thus, we characterize the Gauss–Seidel method, according to (23), by choosing $x_i^{(k)}$ such that

$$x_i^{(k)} = x_i^{(k-1)} + \frac{r_{ii}^{(k)}}{v_{ii}}.$$

33. Now, considering $r_{i+1}^{(k)}$ associated with

$$\mathbf{x}_{i+1}^{(k)} = (x_1^{(k)}, x_2^{(k)}, \dots, x_i^{(k)}, x_{i-1}^{(k-1)}, \dots, x_n^{(k-1)})^T,$$

it follows from (27) that the i -th component of $r_{i+1}^{(k+1)}$ is

$$r_{i,i+1}^{(k)} = h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij}x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij}x_j^{(k-1)} - v_{ii}x_i^{(k)}.$$

34. Since $r_{i,i+1}^{(k)} = 0$ by equation (23), the Gauss–Seidel method can be characterized by choosing $x_{i+1}^{(k)}$ such that the i -th component of $r_{i+1}^{(k)}$ is zero.

35. However, choosing $x_{i+1}^{(k)}$ in such a way as to eliminate one coordinate of the residual vector is not always the most efficient way to reduce $r_{i+1}^{(k)}$. Adjusting the Gauss–Seidel method based on (32),

$$x_i^{(k)} = x_i^{(k-1)} + \omega \frac{r_{ii}^{(k)}}{v_{ii}},$$

for certain positive choices of ω , we obtain a reduction in the norm of the residual vector, which promotes faster convergence.

36. To determine the matrix of the SOR method, it is important to observe that, using equation (29) with $m = i$, we can reformulate equation (35).

37. From (29), we have

$$\omega \frac{r_{ii}^{(k)}}{v_{ii}} + \omega x_i^{(k-1)} = \frac{\omega}{v_{ii}} \left[h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij}x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij}x_j^{(k-1)} \right].$$

38. And from (35), we obtain

$$x_i^{(k)} - x_i^{(k-1)} + \omega x_i^{(k-1)} = \frac{\omega}{v_{ii}} \left[h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij} x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)} \right].$$

39. That is,

$$x_i^{(k)} + (\omega - 1)x_i^{(k-1)} = \frac{\omega}{v_{ii}} \left[h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij} x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)} \right].$$

40. Therefore,

$$x_i^{(k)} = (1 - \omega)x_i^{(k-1)} + \frac{\omega}{v_{ii}} \left[h_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij} x_j^{(k)} - \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij} x_j^{(k-1)} \right],$$

and this last equation characterizes the SOR method.

41. In this way, we can rewrite the last equation as

$$v_{ii}x_i^{(k)} + \omega \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} v_{ij}x_j^{(k)} = (1 - \omega) v_{ii}x_i^{(k-1)} - \omega \sum_{j=i+1}^n v_{ij}x_j^{(k-1)} + \omega h_i.$$

42. Equivalently, considering $V = L + D + R$ as in the Gauss–Seidel method, we have

$$(D + \omega L)^{-1}x^{(k)} = [(1 - \omega)D - \omega R]x^{(k-1)} + \omega h.$$

43. Hence,

$$x^{(k)} = (D + \omega L)^{-1}[(1 - \omega)D - \omega R]x^{(k-1)} + \omega(D + \omega L)^{-1}h.$$

44. If we define

$$T_\omega = (D + \omega L)^{-1}[(1 - \omega)D - \omega R]$$

and

$$c_\omega = \omega(D + \omega L)^{-1}h,$$

we can represent the SOR method by the equation

$$x^{(k)} = T_\omega x^{(k-1)} + c_\omega.$$

Stopping Process

45. In the stopping process of any iterative method, we begin with an initial estimate $x^{(0)}$ for the solution of $Vx = h$.
46. Using this initial estimate and a numerical method, we continuously refine the solution until the desired accuracy is achieved, that is, until a specified number of decimal places is correct.
47. To ensure that the solution has been obtained with the desired accuracy $\varepsilon > 0$, we perform the following test during the iterative process:

$$\frac{\|x^{(k+1)} - x^{(k)}\|_{\infty}}{\|x^{(k+1)}\|_{\infty}} < \varepsilon,$$

where ε is a predefined tolerance, and $x^{(k)}$ and $x^{(k+1)}$ are two consecutive approximations of x . In this case, $x^{(k+1)}$ is taken as the desired solution.

Convergence Criterion

48. **Property:** The iterative process $x^{(k)} = Cx^{(k-1)} + u$ is convergent, provided that $\|C\| < 1$.

Proof of the Property

49. Suppose that the norm of C is less than 1, that is, $\|C\| < 1$. Let us show that this implies convergence of the iterative process.
50. To do this, we consider the following difference, called the error at the k -th iteration:

$$e^{(k)} = x - x^{(k)},$$

where x represents the exact solution that we aim to obtain through the iterative process.

51. Substituting the expression for $x^{(k)}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} e^{(k)} &= x - (Cx^{(k-1)} + u), \\ e^{(k)} &= Cx + u - (Cx^{(k-1)} + u), \\ e^{(k)} &= C(x - x^{(k-1)}). \end{aligned}$$

52. Now observe that this can be rewritten as

$$e^{(k)} = Ce^{(k-1)}.$$

53. This expression shows that the error at the k -th iteration depends linearly on the error at the previous iteration.

54. Since the norm of C is less than 1, the magnitude of the error decreases at each iteration, which implies convergence of the iterative process.

55. In fact, by applying successive iterations, we obtain

$$e^{(k)} = C^k e^{(0)},$$

where $e^{(0)}$ is the initial error of the process.

56. Therefore,

$$\|e^{(k)}\| \leq \|C\|^k \|e^{(0)}\|.$$

57. Since $\|C\| < 1$, we have $\|C\|^k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

58. Consequently, $\|e^{(k)}\| \rightarrow 0$, which means that $x^{(k)} \rightarrow x$.

59. Therefore, the iterative process is convergent.

One-Dimensional Poisson Problem

60. The Poisson equation describes how a scalar potential, or field, is influenced by a distribution of charges or masses in a given space.

61. In computational practice, solving the Poisson equation often involves discretizing the space into a grid or mesh. This leads to the formation of a system of linear equations, where each node in the grid corresponds to a variable in the system. The resulting matrix is generally sparse, since most grid points do not directly interact with one another due to the localization of the charges.

62. **Definition 4.** Let Ω be a connected set in \mathbb{R}^n and $\partial\Omega$ its boundary. The Poisson equation can be defined by

$$-\Delta u = f(x),$$

where Δ denotes the Laplace operator, or Laplacian.

63. Here, $f(x)$ is the source function and must satisfy the condition

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x) dx = 0,$$

that is, the integral of $f(x)$ over the domain must be zero.

64. This condition ensures that the solution u can be expressed in terms of a harmonic function.

65. Harmonic functions are solutions of the Laplace equation $\Delta u = 0$.

Solution of the Poisson Problem

66. To solve the Poisson equation, the Dirichlet condition is commonly used, which allows solving boundary value problems on a specific interval.

67. In the one-dimensional case ($n = 1$), the Dirichlet problem for the Poisson equation on an interval $I = (0, 1)$ consists of finding a function $u(x)$ that satisfies

$$\begin{cases} -u''(x) = f(x), & \text{if } x \in I \\ u(0) = a \text{ and } u(1) = b, \end{cases}$$

where $u(0) = a$ and $u(1) = b$ are the boundary conditions.

68. The approximation of the function u is obtained using Taylor expansions of u around a point $x_0 \in I$, both to the right and to the left, with $h > 0$, given respectively by

$$u(x_0 + h) = u(x_0) + u'(x_0)h + \frac{1}{2}u''(x_0)h^2 + \frac{1}{6}u'''(x_0)h^3 + \dots,$$

$$u(x_0 - h) = u(x_0) - u'(x_0)h + \frac{1}{2}u''(x_0)h^2 - \frac{1}{6}u'''(x_0)h^3 + \dots$$

69. Adding the expansions, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} u(x_0 + h) + u(x_0 - h) &= 2u(x_0) + (u'(x_0)h - u'(x_0)h) \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{1}{2}u''(x_0)h^2 + \frac{1}{2}u''(x_0)h^2 \right) \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{1}{6}u'''(x_0)h^3 - \frac{1}{6}u'''(x_0)h^3 \right) + \dots \end{aligned}$$

70. Simplifying like terms, we have

$$u(x_0 + h) + u(x_0 - h) = 2u(x_0) + 2\left(\frac{1}{2}u''(x_0)h^2\right) + \dots$$

71. Hence,

$$u(x_0 + h) + u(x_0 - h) = 2u(x_0) + u''(x_0)h^2 + \dots$$

72. Consequently,

$$u''(x_0) \approx \frac{u(x_0 - h) - 2u(x_0) + u(x_0 + h)}{h^2} + O(h^2).$$

73. Here, h is the step size used in the discretization, and $O(h^2)$ denotes the error term, which decreases as h decreases.

74. The interval $[0, 1]$ is discretized into $n + 1$ subintervals of length

$$h = \frac{1}{n + 1},$$

yielding n interior points between 0 and 1 .

75. We adopt the notation

$$u_i = u(x_i) \quad \text{and} \quad f_i = f(x_i),$$

to represent the values of the function u and the source function f at the discretized points.

76. Using the three-point formula, with $1 \leq i \leq n$, we discretize the differential equation given in (67) by finite differences:

$$\frac{-u_{i-1} + 2u_i - u_{i+1}}{h^2} = f_i.$$

77. This leads to a linear system of n equations in n unknowns:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{h^2}(2u_1 - u_2) = f_1 + ah^{-2} \\ \frac{1}{h^2}(-u_1 + 2u_2 - u_3) = f_2 \\ \vdots \\ \frac{1}{h^2}(-u_{n-2} + 2u_{n-1} - u_n) = f_{n-1} \\ \frac{1}{h^2}(-u_{n-1} + 2u_n) = f_n + bh^{-2}. \end{cases}$$

78. The previous system can be written in matrix form as $Vu = f$, where V is a tridiagonal, symmetric, and sparse matrix given by

$$\frac{1}{h^2} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & & & \\ -1 & 2 & -1 & & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & -1 & 2 & -1 \\ & & & & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ \vdots \\ u_{n-1} \\ u_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_1 + ah^{-2} \\ f_2 \\ \vdots \\ f_{n-1} \\ f_n + bh^{-2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

79. We solve numerically the linear system $Vu = f$ in order to obtain the approximate solution u at the discretized points.

Application of the Poisson Equation Using Iterative Methods

80. Now that we have formulated the linear system (77), we will apply the Gauss–Seidel and SOR methods to solve it, determining an approximate solution at the discretized points.

81. This procedure will provide us with a numerical solution for the one-dimensional Poisson equation with specified boundary conditions.

82. To determine this numerical solution, we use MATLAB, which facilitates the implementation and analysis of the results.

83. **Example 1.** Let us consider the function

$$f(x) = \sin(2\pi x).$$

84. We need to show that this function satisfies condition (63), with $\Omega = [0, 1]$.

85. Indeed, let us compute the integral

$$\int_0^1 \sin(2\pi x) dx = \left[-\frac{1}{2\pi} \cos(2\pi x) \right]_0^1 = 0.$$

86. Therefore, we have shown that the function $f(x) = \sin(2\pi x)$ satisfies the condition.

87. Now, after discretizing the function with $n = 100$ according to (76), with $h = (\frac{1}{100+1})$, we obtain the system in the form $Vu = f$:

$$10201 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 2 & -1 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ \vdots \\ u_{99} \\ u_{100} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0622 \\ 0.1241 \\ 0.1855 \\ \vdots \\ -0.1241 \\ -0.0621 \end{bmatrix} .$$

88. Using the Gauss–Seidel method with tolerance $\epsilon < 10^{-3}$, we achieve convergence after 413 iterations, obtaining as a result the vector

$$u = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0012 \\ 0.0025 \\ 0.0037 \\ 0.0049 \\ \vdots \\ -0.0025 \\ -0.0013 \end{bmatrix} .$$

89. The following figure represents this result.

Figure 1: Numerical solution of the one-dimensional Poisson problem for Example 1 obtained using the Gauss–Seidel method.

90. When we use the SOR method, with tolerance $\epsilon < 10^{-3}$ and $\omega = 1.80$, we achieve convergence after 127 iterations.

91. Thus, we obtain the vector

$$u = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0016 \\ 0.0033 \\ 0.0049 \\ 0.0065 \\ \vdots \\ -0.0030 \\ -0.0015 \end{bmatrix}.$$

92. This result is represented by the following figure.

Figure 2: Numerical solution of the one-dimensional Poisson problem for Example 1 obtained using the Successive Over-Relaxation (SOR) method.

93. The appropriate choice of ω not only accelerates convergence but also contributes to the stability of the iterative process, ensuring that the iterations remain convergent.

94. **Example 2.** Let us now consider the function

$$f(x) = e^x.$$

95. When verifying whether this function satisfies condition (63), with $\Omega = [0, 1]$, we have

$$\int_0^1 e^x dx = [e^x]_0^1 = e - 1.$$

96. Therefore, the function does not satisfy the condition.

97. Discretizing the function with $n = 100$, according to (76), we obtain the system in the form $Vu = f$:

$$10201 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 2 & -1 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \\ \vdots \\ u_{99} \\ u_{100} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0100 \\ 1.0200 \\ 1.0301 \\ \vdots \\ 2.6650 \\ 2.6916 \end{bmatrix}.$$

98. Using the Gauss–Seidel method with tolerance $\epsilon < 10^{-3}$, we obtain a result represented by the following figure.

Figure 3: Numerical solution of the one-dimensional Poisson problem for Example 2 obtained using the Gauss–Seidel method.

99. When applying the SOR method, with tolerance $\epsilon < 10^{-3}$ and $\omega = 1.60$, we obtain a result represented by the following figure.

Figure 4: Numerical solution of the one-dimensional Poisson problem for Example 2 obtained using the Successive Over-Relaxation (SOR) method.

100. Condition (63) ensures that the source function behaves properly over the entire domain, without irregularities or undesirable behavior, such as discontinuity or uncontrolled growth. This aspect is fundamental for the accuracy of iterative methods, since poorly behaved functions may lead to significant numerical errors. Furthermore, Figures 3 and 4 clearly show distinct numerical solutions for the problem defined in (94). This difference between the solutions may be related to the fact that the considered function does not satisfy condition (63).

Final Remarks

101. This article addressed the one-dimensional Poisson problem, which leads to a sparse matrix and requires the use of iterative methods to determine the solution. To apply these methods, it was first necessary to formulate the corresponding linear system, using the Dirichlet condition to solve the Poisson equation and the finite difference method to perform the discretization.
102. Furthermore, when choosing source functions to solve differential equations, such as the Poisson equation, by means of iterative numerical

methods, it is essential to ensure that the function is integrable over the domain under consideration. This guarantees that the iterative methods operate properly, producing accurate and convergent results for the numerical solution of the differential equation.

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[12]

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Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [11].

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